

My Little Epiphanies: A Diagram to Create Heaven in Disaster

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My Little Epiphanies by Aisha Chaudhary is a masterpiece literature which is not a mere detail of a daring little girl who wished to live a full life in a very short span of her life. In *My Little Epiphanies*, she addresses her own sentiments as well as what provided her a sense of hope and power throughout her own difficult time in life. This book provided her with a bigger purpose, and it provided her with something to hang onto in difficult times. Aisha's minor epiphanies have sometimes shown themselves in the form of drawings that encapsulate what was moving on in her head as her destiny unfolded. A book about her odd life was her goal; she thought that it would help others who were experiencing similar challenges to achieve peace as she had. Aisha was diagnosed with SCID at birth and struggled with it for 18 years. She enjoys watching Bollywood films with her mother. She became a huge fan of Shonali Bhowmik after seeing the trailer for *Margrita with A Straw* and wanted to see the film before she died. She received a bone marrow transplant but was unable to fully recover because the bone marrow did not completely match. This book provides the reader with insight into what was going on inside Aisha's head. She was a strong girl who had lived her life to the fullest.

The prologue and introduction are both heart-breaking and profound. Aisha has perfectly expressed herself through quotations. Aisha's drawings or doodles are also included in the book. It was important to Aisha that her readers understood the definition of the phrase "epiphanies," which is why she picked such a difficult title for her book. Because, after all, we read to understand, don't we? That level of maturity at the age of 18 is really exceptional. We are in a vulnerable stage in our lives, during which we investigate and experiment extensively. Aisha, on the other hand, had already gone through and seen enough. Well that's what her epiphanies provide for the rest of us. The preface, prologue, preface, and epilogue all contribute to a greater understanding of the author's character. Then there are the "aha" moments that she has. Her epiphanies are told via her tales, which are quick, sweet, and hard-hitting. They have acquired wisdom and maturity. Because of this, they reveal just how much Aisha learned regarding life in such a small space of time. While we, as grownups, strive and fail to comprehend life; while we grieve over petty concerns and for something we don't have, this little soul not only realised the core of life, but she also shared her wisdom with each of us via the publication of this book. Mark the tormentation of life in the lines of Aisha:

Fairy dust in your eyes
I could see no more
They say the soul never dies
What did yours leave me for
My darling you have kept me alive
You soothed the rocky roads before me
I'm shattered now you're dead inside. (Chaudhary)

This book is her way of letting her thoughts away from the pain and the misery she has always been in. Spending most of her time lying on the bed, this book is about a lifetime of her experiences. This book is full of honest, mischief, kindness, pain, hope and above all love. Reading this book makes one feel how little our life and problems are compared to what this young girl went through in her short but eventful life. One statement which is echoed throughout the book, and something that is always attempted to live by, "We should be happy about the things we can do instead of being sad about things we are not capable of".

Her beautiful doodles and short poems so well capture the myriad of emotions she goes through while she battles this monster of a disease and how she does it all with a smile on her face. Shekhar Kapoor, an Indian Film maker says, "Aisha, your each breath is worth a thousand of ours, your each moment expands into million of ours, your love for, and deep understanding of what life is, open a door for us to peek into our own, in a roomful of mirrors where your each word reflect our lives, thank you for opening our eyes, and for the love." (Kapoor) Her optimism touches the shores of ultimate joy when she says:

Why is sadness so unattractive?

Sadness is attracted to me.

I am sad because I am sad.

I despise the feelings that come with jealousy.(Chaudhary 22)

"We should be happy about the things we can do instead of being sad about the things we can't do," says one statement repeated throughout the book. It is written from the heart of a young girl who still has so much she wants to do in life but is struggling with the fact that her illness is taking over. When confronted with fear, pain, and questions about death, Aisha takes a new path—creating with flourish. Her thought for love is quite different when she says that man is so selfish that he cannot be fully in love with anybody because he is more obsessed with his desires and behave accordingly. For her, friends are a great assistance to all of us, but relatives are the people who make our destiny and obviously they make it worst which we cannot avoid. Her simple and powerful message throughout her life was to be happy, to choose happiness every day. She demonstrated this by living life to the fullest because losing something so significant had taught her to appreciate the smallest of things. She is amazed to find that people meditate so much over the future prospects and do not think a little about the present which is the pathway to future. She was not a common girl as it is simply impossible to tolerate such a jot and these disastrous situations are enough to give anybody a nervous breakdown. In spite of suffering incessantly, she gave beautiful flashes to live a healthy and satisfactory life.

Throughout the short book, profound messages are written in the most straightforward and honest manner. You'll learn something new if you read them again. Isn't that how it is in real life? As you savour each moment with gratitude, you will discover something that will make you a little kinder, a little wiser, and a little more like the person you were born to be. The book is a sweet and realistic depiction of the essence of life as seen through the eyes of a young girl who recognised its worth. We all need a reminder every now and then that it's okay if we only manage to survive some days. But what about the other days? We should reach for the sky and paint it in whatever colours we want, because the sky is pink, blue, and even green. The sky can be any colour you want it to be. The book is full of practical wisdom and the interesting thing is this that. The book ends with:

Black sunshine, baby

Why do you hurt me so

My eyes cry when it's rainy

My heart melts in the snow

You tear me to shreds and bits.(Chaudhary 68)

WORKS CITED

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- [2]. Kapoor, Shekhar. *Book Review: My Little Epiphanies*. 12 April 2015. 5 January 2020. <<https://www.r4review.com/my-little-epiphanies/>>.